

A study on in vivo validation of traditionally used medicinal plant *Lasia spinosa* on uterus and cervix of cyclic female mice

Sonam Doima, Krishnakshi Misra, Archana Saikia and Hirendra Nath Sarma

Department of Zoology, Rajiv Gandhi University, Arunachal Pradesh
Corresponding E-mail: sonam.doima@rgu.ac.in

The tribal communities in Northeast (NE) India have been using the abundant resource of herbal medicines since ancient times to cure ailments including conditions related to women's health. Among many others, the traditional healing practices utilising the plant *Lasia spinosa* against dysmenorrhea by certain communities of Arunachal Pradesh and Assam led to the need for the scientific validation of the healing properties of this plant for female reproduction. This study was carried out to identify the cause of therapeutic effect of *L. spinosa* on female cyclic mice through histological study of uterine and cervix tissues. Crude root extract (CRE) of *L. spinosa* has been prepared by soaking the crude root powder in methanol for 72 hours. The CRE has been administered to adult female cyclic mice for two consecutive estrous cycle (for 8 days) beginning with the morning of proestrus. The histology of uterus and cervix has been studied using routine Hematoxylin and Eosin staining. The uterine tissues of the treated mice showed significant hyperproliferation of uterine endometrial epithelium and increase in number of uterine glands as compared to the control group. The epithelial cellular proliferation can be seen in the treated cervix as compared to the control group. The stroma of the cervix is more compact in the control group.

Keywords: *Lasia spinosa*, female reproduction, traditional healing, uterine histology.